

Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for NRT Sentinel 4 SO₂ plume height

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present document is the Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) describing the theoretical basis and the implementation of the SO₂ LH product for MTG-S/Sentinel-4 measurements.

The purpose of the document is to give detailed mathematical description of the algorithm and to discuss the necessary input and auxiliary data, and the output that will be generated. In addition, information about the expected size of the product, expected calculation times, and the expected accuracy are provided.

Note that the current version of the ATBD is based on the Sentinel-5p Innovation Sulphur dioxide layer height (S5P+I: SO₂ LH) project ATBD [RD10], i.e. it was originally written for Sentinel-5p/TROPOMI. At the time of writing this document, MTG-S was not launched. Once dedicated in-flight measurements and instrument characteristics are available, this document will be updated accordingly, representing the Sentinel-4 SO₂ LH retrieval. The basic algorithmic background and training however will remain the same, only the input parameters will be updated using the Sentinel-4 instrumental slit function information and information about instrument viewing angles.

2 APPLICABLE AND REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

2.1 Applicable documents

[AD01] MTG UVN Level 0 & 1 Format Specification;
source: EUM **ref:** EUM/MTG/SPE/10/0453; **issue:** v5B **date:** 2019-09-11

2.2 Reference documents

- [RD01] Sentinel-4 Level 2 Terms and symbols used in the ATBDs;
source: DLR; **ref:** S4-L2-DLR-ATBD-2019; **issue:** 1.0; **date:** 2017-05-15
- [RD02] GMES Sentinels 4 and 5 Mission Requirements Document (MRD);
source: ESA; **ref:** EO-SMA-/1507/JL; **issue:** 3; **date:** 2011-09-21
- [RD03] GMES Sentinel-4&5 Mission Requirements Traceability Document (MRTD);
source: ESA; **ref:** EOP-SM/2413/BV-bv; **date:** 2012
- [RD04] Report Of The Review Of User Requirements For Sentinels-4/-5;
source: ESA; **ref:** EO-SMA-/1507/JL; **issue:** 2.1; **date:** 2011-12-21
- [RD05] S5P/TROPOMI SO₂ ATBD;
source: BIRA-IASB; **ref:** S5P-BIRA-L2-400E-ATBD; **issue:** 2.7.0; **date:** 2024-10-07.
- [RD06] S4 Sulfur dioxide ATBD;
source: DLR; **ref:** S4-L2-DLR-ATBD-2005; **issue:** 3.9; **date:** 2024-02-29
- [RD07] Sentinel-5 Level-2 Prototype Processor Development Requirements Specification.
source: ESA; **ref:** S5-RS-ESA-GR-0131; **issue:** 1.7.
- [RD08] Sentinel-4 Instrument Design
source: ESA; **ref:** S4-L2-ESA-TEC-2016; **issue:** 1.0; **date:** 2016-04-13
- [RD09] Sentinel-4 Level-2 Product User Manual for SO₂;
source: DLR; **ref:** S4-L2-DLRPUM-4105; **issue:** 2.5; **date:** 2023-11-30.
- [RD10] S5p+I - SO₂LH ATBD
Source: DLR, **ref:** S5P+I-SO₂LH-D4-ATBD-v4, **issue:** 4.0, **date:** 2021-07-16

3 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

A list of abbreviations and acronyms which are used throughout this document is given below:

AAI	Aerosol absorption index
ALH	Aerosol layer height
AOD	Aerosol optical depth
AK	Averaging kernel
AIRS	Atmospheric InfraRed Sounder
AMF	Airmass factor
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
BRDF	Bidirectional reflectance distribution function
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (German Aerospace Centre)
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
DU	Dobson Unit
EISF	Extended Iterative Spectral Fitting
ESA	European Space Agency
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FP_ILM	Full Physics Inverse Learning Machine
IASI	Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer
ISRF	Instrument Spectral Response Function
IMF	Remote Sensing Technology Institute
LIDORT	Linearized Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer
LH	Layer Height
LER	Lambertian Equivalent Reflectivity
LUT	Look-up table
MLPR	MultiLayer Perceptron Regression
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder
MSE	Mean squared error
NN	Neural Network
NRT	Near real time
PBL	Planetary Boundary Layer
PC	Principal component
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCR	Principal Component Regression
O ₃	Ozone
OE	Optimal Estimation
OMI	Ozone Monitoring Instrument
RAA	Relative azimuth angle
RRS	Rotational Raman Scattering
RTM	Radiative transfer model
S5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
S5 L2PP	Sentinel-5 Level 2 Prototype Processor
SAA	Solar azimuth angle
SAF	Satellite Application Facility
SCD	Slant column density
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
SZA	Solar zenith angle
TOA	Top of Atmosphere
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Ozone Measurement Instrument
UV	Ultra Violet
VAA	Viewing azimuth angle
VCD	Vertical column density
VZA	Viewing zenith angle

4 Introduction to the S4 sulphur dioxide layer height product

4.1 Sentinel-4 instrument

Sentinel 4 (S4) is an operational satellite mission providing atmospheric composition data over the European geographical domain with a fast (hourly) revisit time. The S4 mission is defined as an Ultraviolet Visible Near-infrared (UVN) spectrometer on each of the geostationary Meteosat Third Generation Sounder (MTG-S) platforms, relying synergy with subsets of data from the MTG-Infra Red Sounder (IRS) on board the same platforms and from the MTG Flexible Combined Imager (FCI) on board the MTG-I platforms.

Key features of the S4/UVN instrument are the spectral range from 305 nm to 500 nm with a spectral resolution of 0.5 nm and a sampling ratio of 3 for the UV/Visible, and 750 nm to 775 nm with a spectral resolution of 0.12 nm in the Near-infrared (NIR), in combination with a low polarization sensitivity and a high radiometric accuracy (3% absolute, 0.05% relative spectral).

The spatial sampling distance varies across the geographic coverage area and takes a value of 8x8 km² at a reference location at 45° N. There are about 550 pixels in the north-to-south direction and about 580 pixels in a single east-to-west scan. A daily Earth observation will consist of about 16 to 20 one-hour east-to-west scans.

S4 will be able to measure in near-real-time a host of atmospheric trace gas species, including sulphur dioxide (SO₂), in support to the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). S4 over Europe, the Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution (TEMPO) mission over the US and the Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer (GEMS) covering East Asia, will form the geostationary fleet of sensors monitoring atmospheric pollution at hourly rate over the most industrial parts of the world. It will complement the global data from the polar orbiting Sentinel-5 Precursor (S5p) and Sentinel-5 (S5) instruments.

A description of the instrument characteristics of S4 and its observation geometry can be found in [RD08].

4.2 Product description & Heritage

Volcanic eruptions eject large amounts of ash (aerosols) and trace gases such as SO₂ into the atmosphere. The ability to quantify the spatial extent and actual magnitude of these ejecta was shown to have a considerable impact on air traffic safety as well as on human health, i.e. acute respiratory irritation and long term diseases. SO₂ oxidizes in the atmosphere to form sulfate particles (PM), which can penetrate deep into the lungs and contribute further to respiratory diseases.

Regular and comprehensive ground-based monitoring, i.e. with the ability for proper quantitative forewarning on the eruptive magnitude, is carried out at only a limited number of volcanoes. The vast amount of continuously erupting volcanoes is remotely located and hence ground-based monitoring is very limited. Hence, near-real-time (NRT) global observations of SO₂ total vertical column density (VCD), SO₂ layer height (henceforth, SO₂ LH) and aerosol load derived from satellite measurements provide unique and important information to quantitatively assess the possible impact of volcanic eruptions on air traffic control and public safety. The need for operational as well as accurate (≤2km in altitude) SO₂ LH information became quite pronounced shortly after the Eyjafjallajökull (2010) and Grimsvötn (2011) eruptions.

Based on UV earthshine measurements, SO₂ VCD can be retrieved easily using for example the Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS) technique (see e.g. Rix et al., 2012), or a Principal Component Analysis (PCA, see e.g. Li et al., 2017). These methods are fast enough for near-real-time (NRT) retrievals. Nevertheless, current operational DOAS and PCA algorithms retrieve only the slant column density (SCD). In order to calculate the VCD, explicit or implicit assumptions about the vertical distribution of SO₂ have to be made to determine the effective light path - this VCD conversion factor is called the Air Mass Factor (AMF). In the UV range between 305 - 335nm, AMFs are calculated by means of multiple-scattering radiative transfer models (RTM) using known or assumed vertical distributions of

SO₂. In these models also the spectral contribution of O₃ has to be considered since it interferes with SO₂ absorption lines.

The SO₂ VCD is strongly dependent on the vertical distribution of SO₂ (in terms of the plume layer height), a quantity which is usually unknown at the time of the measurement. Even if there are ground-based or aircraft measurements of the SO₂ LH, the data are generally difficult to use for validation, since usually the number of collocations is small for small plumes. Only for strong eruptions, volcanic plumes are typically transported over long distances increasing the possibility to observe the plume with different instrument. Thus, for volcanic SO₂ measurements, the vertical distribution of SO₂ is a key parameter limiting the product accuracy.

The direct determination of the vertical distribution of SO₂ based on satellite data is, unsurprisingly, challenging, since the information about the vertical distribution is not easily extracted from the spectral signature (see Yang et al., 2009 and Nowlan et al., 2011). The SO₂ loading (or VCD) has a direct effect on the optical depth, whereas the layer height has an indirect effect on the optical depth since it influences both the number of photons passing through the SO₂ layer as well as the layer optical depth due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-sections (Yang et al., 2009). The altitude of an SO₂ layer determines the proportion of backscattered photons that pass through this absorbing layer towards the sensor. Clearly, more photons are Rayleigh-backscattered in the overlying atmosphere when the layer is lower in the atmosphere, resulting in fewer photons transmitted through the layer, and vice versa.

To date, direct SO₂ plume height retrievals using satellite UV backscatter measurements from e.g. the OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) or GOME-2 (Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2) are very time-consuming, since the spectral information content and its characterization require computationally demanding radiative transfer modelling: Yang et al., 2009 developed an Extended Iterative Spectral Fitting (EISF) algorithm for the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) aboard the NASA Aura satellite, which iteratively solves the linear fit equation by minimizing differences between measurements and forward model computations. Nowlan et al., 2011 uses an optimal estimation (OE, Rodgers, 2000) scheme for the retrieval of the SO₂ VCD and LH based on Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2 instrument (GOME-2) data.

Recently, new algorithms have been developed that are much faster than direct fitting approaches. The Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB) have developed an SO₂ LH algorithm in the framework of the Sentinel-5 L2PP SO₂ product development which is conceptually quite close to the EISF algorithm using a look-up-table (LUT) approach to replace the radiative transfer calculations. It is based on a modified DOAS algorithm where SO₂ optical depth (OD) spectra are used in the DOAS fit. Hedelt et al., 2019 have developed an algorithm called 'Full-Physics Inverse Learning Machine' (hereafter referred to as FP_ILM) for the retrieval of the SO₂ LH based on Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI data using a coupled Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Neural Network (NN) approach including regression. This algorithm is an improvement of the original FP_ILM algorithm developed by Efremenko et al., 2017 for the retrieval of the SO₂ LH based on GOME-2 data using a Principal Component Regression (PCR) technique.

In general, the FP_ILM algorithm creates a mapping between the spectral radiance and atmospheric parameter using machine learning methods. The time-consuming training phase of the algorithm using radiative transfer model calculations is performed off-line, and only the inversion operator has to be applied to satellite measurements - this makes the algorithm extremely fast and it can thus be used in near-real time processing environments.

The FP_ILM SO₂ LH algorithm was implemented in the operational Sentinel-5p/TROPOMI SO₂ retrieval in August 2024, see [RD05]. Note that Fedkin et al., 2020 have applied FP_ILM algorithm to retrieve the SO₂ LH based on OMI data. The FP_ILM algorithm has also been used for the retrieval of ozone profile shapes (Xu et al., 2017) and the retrieval of surface properties accounting for bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) effects (Loyola et al., 2020).

4.3 Requirements

Independent information on the SO₂ height can be obtained typically when the SO₂ signal is strong enough, i.e. greater than about 10-30 DU (see e.g. Nowlan et al., 2011).

The scientific requirements formulated for the development of an SO₂ product for the upcoming Sentinel-5 satellite (see [RD4]) are followed, which specify an uncertainty of the SO₂ LH to be smaller than 1 km (breakthrough) to 2 km (threshold) for SO₂ VCD \geq 25 DU (Requirement S5-L2-PRO-220 in [RD4]). In addition, it was agreed with the end-user ECMWF/CAMS (A. Inness, pers. Comm.) to impose stricter requirements, see **TBD READING NOTE?**

Requirement	Value
SO ₂ LH (threshold)	<2km for SO ₂ VCD >15 DU
SO ₂ LH (baseline)	<1km for SO ₂ VCD >20 DU

5 ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

Conceptually, the FP_ILM SO₂ LH algorithm consists of a training phase, in which the inversion operator is obtained using synthetic data generated with an appropriate radiative transfer model, and an operational phase, in which the inversion operator is applied to the satellite measurements. The main advantage of the FP_ILM over classical direct fitting approaches is that the time-consuming training phase involving complex RT modeling is performed offline; the inverse operator itself is robust and computationally simple and therefore extremely fast. The algorithm relies on the algorithm described in Hedelt et al., 2019 with some differences in the algorithm settings.

The FP_ILM SO₂ LH algorithm makes direct use of the Sentinel-4 L2 SO₂ product. It will be triggered for pixels exceeding a certain SO₂ threshold (as defined in the following). The output parameters of the algorithm are the SO₂ LH, an optimized SO₂ VCD and AMF as well as error estimates.

5.1 Training phase

5.1.1 Generation of training dataset

During the training phase, the Linearized Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer model (LIDORT) with inelastic rotational Raman scattering (RRS) implementation (Spurr et al., 2008) is deployed to compute a simulated high-resolution (i.e. $\Delta\lambda = 0.05$ nm) reflectance spectra LUT in the wavelength range 311–335 nm. These spectra depend upon the following input parameters: the SO₂ VCD and LH, the surface albedo, the surface height, the O₃ VCD, the solar zenith angle (SZA), the viewing zenith angle (VZA) and the relative azimuth angle (RAA). Note that O₃ VCD has to be included due to the strong spectral interference between SO₂ and O₃ in the spectral range considered.

O₃ profiles are classified according to the total column amount of ozone as specified in the TOMS Version 7 O₃ profile climatology (McPeters et al., 1998). The SO₂ plume profile is taken to have a Gaussian profile, characterized by the total SO₂ VCD loading and centered at a layer height z_{SO_2} , along with a width fixed to 2.5 km FWHM. In the following, the retrieval of SO₂ LH refers to the retrieval of the SO₂ layer mid-height z_{SO_2} . Simulations were performed on a pressure/temperature/height grid from the US standard atmosphere. Note that the original vertical grid resolution has been increased to a resolution of 0.25 km below 15 km altitude in order to properly resolve the SO₂ plume shape. Temperature-dependent absorption cross-sections of O₃ from (Serdyuchenko et al., 2014) and SO₂ from Bogumil et al., 2003 were used.

In total, 541,345 simulated reflectance spectra have been calculated on a selective parameter grid established by means of a smart sampling technique developed by Loyola et al. (2016). Table 1 lists all input parameter for the LIDORT-RRS model. After an extended sensitivity study, Table 2 shows a summary of the final optimized parameter space for which in total 541,345 reflectance spectra have been simulated, which will be used for training and validating the algorithm. Note that in principle a broader training parameter range can be used, however the error in the NN retrieval increases when increasing the parameter range.

The simulated high-resolution reflectance spectra are convolved with the Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF). The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is about 1000 in the SO₂ wavelength range. Thus, to account for instrumental noise in the training phase, uncorrelated Gaussian noise with a fixed SNR of 1000 is added to the simulated spectral data.

The spectral dataset is randomly split into a training dataset (consisting of 90% of the entire dataset, i.e. 487,210 spectra) and a test dataset (consisting of 10% of the entire dataset, i.e. 54,135 spectra). The training dataset is used to train the PCA and NN operators and the test dataset is used to test the performance of the trained operators on untrained data.

The training spectra LUT forms the input of machine learning training phase, which is outlined hereafter. A flow diagram of the FP_ILM training algorithm is shown in Figure 1

Table 1 LIDORT-RRS input parameters for generating reflectance spectra

Parameter	Source
O ₃ cross-section	[Serdyuchenko et al., 2014]
SO ₂ cross-section	[Bogumil et al., 2003]
Temperature/Pressure profile	US standard profile based on [Lamsal et al., 2004], with finer gridding in lower atmosphere
O ₃ profile	TOMS v7 [McPeters et al., 1998]
SO ₂ profile	Gaussian SO ₂ profile with 2.5 km FWHM at varying LH z_{SO_2}

Table 2 Physical parameters varied for the generation of reflectance spectra.

Parameter	Range
SZA	0 – 75°
VZA	0 – 60°
RAA	0 – 180°
Surface albedo	0.0 – 0.5
Surface pressure	10121 – 372 mbar
O ₃ VCD	225 – 525 DU
SO ₂ VCD	0.5 – 1000 DU
SO ₂ LH	0.5 – 25 km

Figure 1 Flow diagram of the training of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH inversion operator

5.1.2 Principal Component Analysis

To extract the information about the layer height and to reduce the dimensionality of the spectral dataset, a PCA is applied to the simulated training spectra. By thus characterizing the set of simulated measurements with fewer parameters, a simpler, more stable and computationally efficient inversion scheme can be realized.

The PCA is performed using the following steps:

1. Scaling of the spectral dataset with $d = 161$ wavelength grid points. PC scores are highly sensitive to data scaling, and scaling of features prior to PCA assigns equal importance to all features. All

reflectance spectra were scaled to the range [-0.9,0.9] using the minimum and maximum reflectance of all training reflectance spectra.

2. Construction of the covariance matrix, which stores the pairwise covariances between the different features.
3. Decomposition of the covariance matrix into its eigenvectors and eigenvalues. The eigenvectors of the covariance matrix represent the principal components (PCs, i.e. the directions of maximum variance), whereas the corresponding eigenvalues define their magnitude.
4. Sort the eigenvalues by decreasing order to rank the corresponding eigenvectors.
5. Select N_{PC} eigenvectors which correspond to the N_{PC} largest eigenvalues, where N_{PC} is the dimensionality of the new feature subspace ($N_{PC} \leq d$)
6. Construct a projection matrix W_{PCA} from the leading N_{PC} eigenvectors, which can be used to transform a dataset X (here: a high-resolution reflectance spectrum) onto the PCA subspace X' , i.e. reducing the dimensionality, with $X' = XW_{PCA}$. Transform the d -dimensional input reflectance dataset X (with $d = 161$) using the projection matrix W_{PCA} to obtain the new N_{PC} -dimensional feature subspace

It was found that using $N_{PC} = 10$ principal components is sufficient to retrieve information about the SO₂ LH. These 10 PCs account for 99.991% of the spectral variance. The inclusion of additional PCs did not result in any improvements to LH retrievals, since higher-order PCs are increasingly affected by noise.

5.1.3 Neural Network Training

The dimensionality-reduced reflectance spectra (now with dimension $N_{PC} = 10$ instead of $d = 161$), together with the information about the O₃ VCD, the viewing angles, the surface pressure and albedo of each training data-point, form the input to train a feed-forward artificial neural network (NN) including regression and L2 regularization. Note here that the SO₂ VCD is not part of the training, since it depends directly on the SO₂ layer height due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-section. Note that including the SO₂ SCD from the DOAS fit as a regression parameter does not improve the retrieval results. Moreover, the SO₂ SCD is also dependent on the SO₂LH. In operational SO₂ retrievals therefore a single SO₂ cross-section at a fixed temperature is used.

A Neural Network (NN) computes a function $M(Z, W_{NN})$, where Z is the input pattern and W_{NN} represents the collection of adjustable parameters in the system, i.e. a weight matrix. A cost function (also known as loss function) $E = C(D, M(Z; W_{NN}))$ measures the discrepancy between D , the desired output for the pattern Z and the output produced by the function $M(Z, W_{NN})$. The learning problem thus consists in finding the value W_{NN} that minimizes $E(W_{NN})$. The performance of such a system is estimated by measuring the accuracy on a set of samples disjoint from the training dataset, i.e. on a test dataset.

The training of the NN is thus an iterative process, in which the cost function is minimized in each time step t by computing the partial derivatives of the cost function with respect to the model parameters at each time step in order to update the parameters W_{NN} . This is done using the 'Adam' stochastic gradient-based optimizer, minimizing the Mean Squared Error (MSE) cost function

$$E(W_{NN}) = \frac{1}{2} (D - M(Z, W_{NN}))^2 \quad (1)$$

by iteratively adjusting W_{NN} as follows:

$$W_{NN}(t) = W_{NN}(t - 1) - \eta \frac{\partial E}{\partial W_{NN}} \quad (2)$$

with η being the learning rate, which is set to $\eta = 0.001$. Note that the learning rate as well as other hyperparameters of the NN have a strong influence on the training and the optimal parameters are found empirically.

In case of the learning rate, a higher or lower learning rate might either miss local minima or end up in a local minimum and thus the global minimum might not be found. Furthermore, a L2 regularization term (also known as weight decay, with $\alpha = 1E-5$) is added to the cost function for maximizing the generalization ability of the network. It shrinks model parameters to prevent over-fitting. By building a

complex neural network, it is quite easy to perfectly fit the training dataset. When this model is however evaluated on new data (here the satellite measurements), it performs very poorly. The regularization thus modifies the cost function by adding additional terms that penalize large weight vectors and preferring diffuse weight vectors. NN weights W_{NN} are initialized using the 'Glorot uniform' initializer (see Glorot and Bengio, 2010) and initial NN biases are set to zero.

Prior to the training of the neural network, all input parameters (i.e. the PCs, as well as further input and output parameters) are scaled to the range $[-0.9, 0.9]$, which is optimized for the sigmoid hyperbolic tan activation function $f = \tanh(x)$ of the hidden layers of the NN. Shifting and scaling input parameters allows for a faster convergence of the learning process. Furthermore, the sigmoid activation function gives the neural network nonlinear capabilities. Note that in general input variables to a NN should be uncorrelated, which is the case here since any linear correlations in the input reflectance spectra were removed by applying the PCA. The input layer has the dimension $[16, N_{\text{Spectra}}]$, with N_{Spectra} the number of training samples (i.e. 487,210 samples). The NN is composed of two hidden layers comprising of 40 neurons in the first hidden layer and 10 neurons in the second layer, and with the corresponding SO₂ LH as the output layer, see Figure 2. The NN training is performed using 90% of the training dataset (i.e. 438,489 samples), and 10% of the dataset are set aside as a validation dataset within the NN training (i.e. 48,721 samples).

Figure 2 FP_ILM SO₂ LH Neural Network Topology

5.1.4 FP_ILM inversion operator

Both the PCA projection matrix W_{PCA} and the trained NN form the FP_ILM inversion operator, which is stored together with the scaling parameters of the training dataset. The final trained FP_ILM operator has converged with a validation loss of about $3.8E-04$, a validation score of 0.997 and a validation MSE of around 0.12 km. Figure 3 shows the performance of the FP_ILM training. In the figure, the PCA

explained variance ratio as a function of number of PCs (top-left panel), each PC as a function of wavelength (top-center panel), the NN training loss and validation score (bottom-left and bottom-center panel, respectively) as well as the resulting SO₂ LH as a function of true SO₂ LH (top-right panel) and the difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD (bottom-right panel) are shown. Clearly, no sign of over- or under-fitting are seen in the NN training history. Table 3 shows the correlation, MSE and standard deviation (StdDev) between true and retrieved LH after applying the trained FP_ILM operator to the independent test dataset. Figure 4 shows the SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD for selected heights (colour coded). It is clearly visible that with increasing SO₂ VCD the difference between retrieved and true LH decreases. Already above about SO₂ VCD>20 DU the difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH is below 2 km.

Table 3 FP_ILM performance overview based on closed-loop retrievals

Parameter	Value
R ² regression score	0.998
Pearson correlation coefficient	0.999
MSE	0.11 km
StdDev	0.34 km

Figure 3 FP_ILM training overview:

Top-left: PCA explained variance ratio as a function of number of PCs added in the PCA.

Top-center: Each PC as a function of wavelength with an offset of 0.1.

Bottom-left and -center: NN training loss and validation score as a function of training epoch, respectively.

Top-right: Retrieved SO₂ LH as a function of true SO₂ LH based on test dataset.

Bottom-right: SO₂ LH difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD

Figure 4 SO₂ LH results of closed-loop retrievals using the independent test dataset.
Top panel: Retrieved SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD for spectra with predefined SO₂ LH. Horizontal colored bars represent the true SO₂ LH.
Bottom panel: Difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD. Horizontal colored bars display 2 km (red) and 1 km (blue) difference thresholds.

5.2 Operational phase

In the operational phase the trained FP_ILM SO₂ operators will be applied to measured MTG-S/Sentinel-4 spectral data. A flow diagram of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval algorithm is shown in Figure 5. The retrieval can be divided into five main steps:

Figure 5 Flow diagram of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval in the operational phase. Flowchart copied from S5P+I SO2LH ATBD. TBD: Update flow chart for S4

5.2.1 Data reading and filtering

First, the operational Sentinel-4 L2 SO₂ data is read and pixels are filtered based on the following criteria:

- SO₂ VCD (assuming a 15 km plume height) NV; SO₂ ≥ 15 DU
- Enhanced SO₂ detection flag FlagEnh: SO₂ ≥ 1 (i.e. SO₂ detection)
- SZA ≤ 75 deg
- VZA ≤ 70 deg.

For pixels fulfilling the above criteria the solar irradiance and earth radiance spectra are read from the operational L1b products. Furthermore, pixel viewing geometries and surface properties, as well as coordinates are read from the L2 SO₂ product. Note that the SAA and VAA angles from the L2 product are read to calculate the RAA and the scattering angle.

If no pixel fulfills the filter criteria, the SO₂ LH retrieval is not triggered and no output LH or VCD is generated. Note that generating a (debug) SO₂ LH product for pixels not fulfilling the above filter criteria is not useful since either the information content related to the SO₂ LH is too low in the spectra or the noise due to high viewing angles is too high.

5.2.2 Wavelength calibration

As the second step, the selected spectra are wavelength-calibrated since irradiance and radiance spectra are given on their own wavelength grid. The calibration is performed using the wavelength calibration information already determined during the DOAS fit performed for the main SO₂ product. The resulting calibrated irradiance and radiance spectra are then used to calculate reflectance spectra.

5.2.3 Dimensionality reduction and NN prediction

As the third step, the PCA projection matrix W_{PCA} acquired during the training phase is applied to the reflectance spectra to transform it to a lower dimension. The PCs along with the information about the O₃ VCD, SZA, VZA, scattering angle, surface albedo and surface pressure of each selected pixel forms the input parameters to predict the SO₂ LH using the trained neural network inverse function. All auxiliary parameters are extracted from the L2 SO₂ product. Note that the information about the O₃ VCD as well as cloud parameters in the L2 SO₂ are carbon-copies from the respective operational L2 products.

Prior to applying the NN to the input parameters, all input parameters are scaled to the range [-0.9,0.9] using the training data scaling parameters and the final SO₂ LH is retrieved. In case that one parameter is exceeding the training parameter range, this pixel will be flagged and the QA value will be reduced.

5.2.4 Improved AMF and VCD calculation

As a final step, the retrieved SO₂ LH is used to calculate an improved SO₂ AMF ($M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}$) to convert the background-corrected SO₂ SCD ($N_{S,\text{SO}_2}^{\text{back}}$) from the L2 SO₂ product to an improved SO₂ VCD ($N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}$):

$$N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2} = \frac{N_{S,\text{SO}_2}}{M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}} \quad (3)$$

Note that the altitude-dependent temperature correction of the VCD due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-section is part of the AMF calculation.

The AMF calculation from the operational SO₂ product is adopted here (see [RD06]), which reads an AMF LUT generated with LIDORT version 3.3 (Spurr et al., 2008). The LUT contains box air mass factors dependent on atmospheric pressure and altitude, viewing angle, surface pressure and albedo at three wavelengths (313, 326 and 375 nm), corresponding to three fit windows of the operational L2 product.

5.2.5 QA value calculation

In order to describe the quality of the retrieved SO₂ LH a quality assurance value (qa_value) is assigned to each pixel. The quality assurance value is a numerical value with a range of [0,1], with the convention that a value <0.5 means that the SO₂ LH results for this pixel should be discarded. The qa_value is calculated as follows:

- Initially, $qa_value(i)=1$ for each pixel (i) for which the SO₂ LH retrieval is triggered.
- If one of the L2 input parameters (see Tab. 7) exceeds the training data range (see Tab. 3) the $qa_value(i)$ is decreased by 25%.
- If the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}(i) < 20$ DU, the $qa_value(i)$ is decreased by 25%.
- If the retrieved SO₂ LH $z_{\text{SO}_2}(i) < 0$ km or the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}(i) < 15$ DU (i.e. the initial threshold criterion triggering the SO₂ LH retrieval), the $qa_value(i)$ is set to 0. The corresponding output parameters (see Tab. 8) are set to NaN.

5.2.6 Pixel flagging

In addition to the QA value also a pixel-wise LH flag (lh_flag) is set which is calculated as follows:

- Initially, $lh_flag = 0$ for each pixel (i) for which the SO₂ LH retrieval is triggered (i.e. no errors or warning occurred during the retrieval)
- If one of the L2 input parameters of a given pixel i exceeds the trained data range, the flag is increased by 1 (i.e. input limit warning).
- If the output SO₂ LH $z_{\text{SO}_2}(i)$ of a given pixel i exceeds the trained output data range, the flag is increased by 2 (i.e. output limit warning).
- If the aerosol absorption index $AAI(i) \geq 2$, the flag is increased by 4 (i.e. absorbing ash present warning).
- If the aerosol absorption index $AAI(i) < 0$, the flag is increased by 8 (i.e. non-absorbing sulfate aerosol present warning).

- If the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{V,impr.SO_2}(i) \leq 15DU$ for a given pixel, the flag is increased by 16 (i.e. improved VCD below limit error).
- If the SO₂ LH $z_{SO_2}(i) < 0$ km, the flag is increased by 32 (LH below zero error).

With this flag, the user can easily set-up his own filter. For example, a very conservative user might only use pixels with $lh_flag == 0$ and $qa_value == 1.0$, whereas the common user already gets good results with $lh_flag < 16$ and $qa_value \geq 0.5$.

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